

CULTURAL RELATIONS BETWEEN CHINA AND CENTRAL ASIA

The student of TSUE Corporate governance

Faculty: Adkhamjanov Javokhir

Javohiradhamjanov75@gmail.com

The teacher of TSUE foreign languages

Department: Khikmatov Dilshodjon

Annotation: This article provides information about Chinese and Central Asia's country's relationship, the main goals of China on Central Asia's lands, historical announcements about Central Asia on Chinese literature

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We all know the poem «Uzbek» by Erkin Vahidov. It is in this poem that it is said with the purpose of expressing that our nation has an ancient history :»Let it be slaughtered Afrosiob, let it be slaughtered Orkhon letter. Interested in what an Orkhon letter is ? Orkhon letter is an ancient monument consisting of inscriptions carved in stone 1300 years ago. Who owns these records ? It is considered to be statements that belong to Bilgi-hoqon, who was the head of State 1300 years ago, who carved his advice on Stone 1300 years ago. In that writing, talking about China, he said :» The Chinese people give such items as silk, silver, gold. The people of China are polite in their speech, they deceive the people of far away with gentle words and silk fabrics. And after being brought closer, they carry out their evil. Deceived by the sweet word and cloth of the Chinese people, Turkish people, you have perished a lot.» Is that what was said about the about Chinese exactly 1,300 years ago suitable today ? Chinese Liu Ya Cho will announce his scientific work in 2010. The name of his scientific work is called The «Theory of the Western territory», and in this scientific work it is said that the territories of Central Asia are a gift given to US Chinese by God. Who is Liv Ya Cho ? Liv Ya Cho is a Chinese general. During 2009-2017, the rector of the University, where the Chinese military,

politicians, Military security staff were trained. «Theory of military territory» is taught as a textbook. «At the moment when the Tang Dynasty ruled China, the territories of Central Asia belonged to us, then it was taken away from us by the Arabs, then it fell into the hands of the Mongols, and later it was taken by the Russians. Today, since the peoples of Central Asia have gained independence, we must take it back to ourselves again,» Liu Ya Cho writes in his scientific work, and this scientific work is taught in Chinese textbooks today. This means that the Chinese state is being formed with this idea. The Chinese have a saying: «the conquest of states by Battle is a Level 3 job. Before that, we can impose other countries on ourselves through diplomatic dialogue. But the most noble cheats achieve the goal in ways. For this reason, lying and deception are not considered a crime in Chinese statehood today and his politics is built on deceit. The Chinese trick is suitable for the Central Asian countries, because the Chinese say to burn a burning house. To date, all Central Asian countries have been mired in corruption. Acquaintances of officials give loans to countries that want people who are reconciling the country. In the 1980s, a civil war broke out in Tajikistan. The situation in Tajikistan is unstable and there is a need for help. Russia could not help. Because at that time Russia needed help. In such a situation, Tajikistan turns to China. And took a loan. the Chinese condition was as follows: Tajikistan should become a member of the CIS. And precisely as a result of these debts, China intervened in the politics of Tajikistan and in 2011, it annexed Tajikistan's territory of 1100 square km. In 2013, after buying Tajikistan, it annexed its territory and introduced Uz troops. Outside of it, China used the mines of the Pamir mountains in return for many loans that it did not receive. That's how it is. Most of Uzbekistan's foreign debt is from China. This situation is very dangerous for our future. It is the responsibility of the people not to fall under the influence of China. For this purpose, building a strong parliament, creating a real democratic institution from the system of authoritarian power, which is concentrated in the ashes of one person.

Relationship between China and Central Asia's countries

Interests of China in Central Asia have not changed for several decades of the independence of the states of Central Asia.

It's a security issue at first. In the case of Xinjiang's autonomy, which borders China with these three countries, three political regimes and is considered a very sensitive issue for Beijing, it is very important that the situation in these three countries is stable, the issue of security, the fight against terror, the establishment of cooperation with separatist groups in Xinjiang is generally avoided, and this issue is always relevant.

On this issue, China is always ready to cooperate, and we will see that the economic changes that we observe in the last decade are being built on the basis of a consensus on the issue of security. From this, I cannot say that in recent years there have been new changes in the interests of China.

China established diplomatic relations with the countries of Central Asia 30 years ago. During this period, the scale of trade between the people's Republic of China and the region grew significantly.

Radio Liberty writes with reference to statistics from the Kyrgyz service that trade between China and the countries of Central Asia amounted to \$ 527 million in 1992, while in 2009 this figure reached \$ 25.9 billion.

China's trade turnover with Kyrgyzstan in 2017 amounted to 1 billion dollars, while in 2018 it increased to 2 billion dollars. In 2019, it was 1 billion 816 million dollars. And 2020, due to the pandemic, trade stopped, and about \$ 700 million commodity exchanges were carried out between the two countries.

Trade and economic cooperation is also increasing China's influence on the region. This can be said to play a major role in Beijing's attempt to make major investments in the region and establish bold ties with the local elite as part of a major project called "one space – one way", giving Central Asia a strategic priority.

If you drive from the city of Osh towards the Alai, after 400 kilometers you will reach the territory bordering China. This is a four to six hour drive. Therefore, their attitude towards ethnic shortcomings arouses concern in me. At the same time,

the Chinese may someday claim that some territory of Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, is ours. It's like going for a move... For example, in Tajikistan, we can say that by establishing its military base and lending, China has to some extent established its control. In Kyrgyzstan, too, all the mining industry goes back to China. According to information published on the website of the Ministry of Finance of Kyrgyzstan, the country's external debt from the Export-import Bank of China will amount to \$ 1.8 billion.

The chairman of the Cabinet of Ministers of Kyrgyzstan, Aqilbek Japarov, said at a meeting of Parliament on June 29 that Kyrgyzstan would be separated from the management of three strategically important objects of the country if it did not recover from its debt to China. That is, the Bishkek thermal power center, the alternative Road "South — North" and the power transmission lines "Datka-Kemin" can pass into Chinese control.

Aiming to improve China's global image, Beijing launched several soft power projects in the early 2000s. The main driving force of China in Central Asia, as well as in other regions, is the Confucian institutions. According to the Chinese strategy, Confucius (a traditional Chinese symbol of wisdom) has kata opportunities to attract many people abroad and achieve worldwide distribution.² only at the beginning of the 2000s, the number of students of Confucius Institutes in Central Asia reached 22,270. At each Confucian Institute, students study the Chinese language, history, spiritual and cultural values of China. Teaching Chinese in Confucian institutions and classes was expected to be an effective tool in Central Asian countries to change the vision of Chinese soft power and Chinese for the better. Through the Beijing Confucius Institute, it seeks to spread culture and language, strengthen the attractiveness of China and eliminate such concepts as prejudice, hostility, threat formed in Soviet times.

In 2019, there were 535 Confucian institutions and 1,134 Confucian classes in 158 countries around the world. According to the headquarters of the Hanban/Confucius institute, a state educational institution owned by the Ministry of

education of China, 13 Confucius Institutes operate in Central Asia, including 5 in Kazakhstan, 4 in Kyrgyzstan, 2 in Uzbekistan and 2 Confucius Institutes in Tajikistan.

According to a synopsis report on China's impact on soft power in Kazakhstan, Beijing will try to spread information for cultural and humanitarian events, journalists and media representatives, and will offer affordable treatment with Chinese traditional medicine. In today's world, marked by economic globalization, political multi-polarization and cultural diversification, China is restoring its importance as a major cultural force in the rise to global prestige through economic growth. To this end, a campaign of cultural diplomacy was organized by the state. This term indicates that cultural diplomacy also includes the dimensions of «culture and diplomacy», and this strategy demonstrates changes on both fronts in China. After the introduction of the national strategy of «being Global» in 2001 in the 10th five-year plan, the cultural front announced its strategy of «being global» in 2002, namely the mission of «creating a new brand». The creation of a new image of China and the transformation of China into an international cultural center was expected to be achieved through «penetration into the mainstream international community and mainstream media», according to Sun Jiazhen, then Minister of Culture. Then in 2004, culture became the third pillar of Chinese diplomacy after politics and economics. The government's rhetoric quickly became intertwined with a large investment in various high-level initiatives and a number of important events: from the launch of the Year of Chinese culture in France, Italy, Russia and Australia in 2003, from 2004 to the opening of Confucian institutions (CI) around the world; then in 2010, from the launch of 24-hour cable channels and newspapers abroad (China Daily Asia Weekly and On the diplomatic front, as well as at the Foreign Affairs Conference of Szi Jinping in 2013. Beijing supported a multifaceted approach to «soft power» using cultural tools in Central Asia, while being able to promote its political-economic model as a path of peaceful development and the combination of socialism with Chinese features. He sought to promote Chinese

culture, which has so far remained unknown among the majority of the indigenous population; promoted a model of economic development and tried to reduce the economic grievances that arise from him, by contributing immeasurably to regional development. China also raised the good-neighborly relationship that began in the 1990s to a full strategic alliance level to counter the influence of Western values, which in the 2000s were interpreted as incompatible with Asian values.

Chinese is becoming the second most studied foreign language in Central Asia after English. In addition, China has opened scholarship programs for Central Asian students. According to the data of the Ministry of education of china⁴, in 2018, a total of 492,185 international students from 196 countries studied at 1,004 higher education institutions in China. Kazakhstan ranked tenth in the list with its 11,784 students, just like that, most of the remaining students came from other countries in Central Asia.

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